

Academic Resilience and Adolescent students

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Abstract:- The study aimed to determine the level of academic resilience among higher secondary school students in the Srinagar district of Kashmir. A simple random selection procedure was used to choose 476 students from higher secondary schools in the district of Srinagar as the study's sample. The academic resilience scale, developed by Mallick and Kaur (2016), is a standardised questionnaire that was used to measure academic resilience. The higher secondary school students in Srinagar were found to have average academic resilience. The results also revealed that females outperformed males in showing academic resilience.

Keywords:- Academic Resilience, Gender, Adolescent.

I. INTRODUCTION

Students endure academic and social problems every day in classrooms, institution, homes and communities; these challenges and pressures can undermine their progress and lead to dropout. Nonetheless, despite challenges and challenging conditions, there are students who can adapt to adversity and achieve high levels of academic achievement and success because they believe that effective learning is the consequence of effort and determination, not just talent. These students are referred to as academic resilient students. Academic resilience is defined as “the ability to deal with setbacks, stress or pressure in the classroom” (Gizir, 2004). It is also defined as the enhanced likelihood of achieving academic and other life goals in the face of environmental difficulties produced by early characteristics, settings, and experiences. Academic resilience is a dynamic developmental process that takes into account the range of protective factors, including individual, parental, institutional or socio-environmental factors. All these elements support the child's resilience. “Academically resilient students can turn adversity into inspiration by keeping personal high goals and aspirations, being goal oriented, having solid problem solving skills and being socially competent.” (wang & Gordan, 1994)

➤ Objectives of the Study

The study has been conducted keeping in view the following objectives:

- To study the level of Academic resilience among the adolescent students of district Srinagar.
- To study the level of Academic resilience among the male and female adolescent students of district Srinagar.

II. METHODS OF THE STUDY

❖ *Descriptive survey method was adopted for the study.*

➤ Population and Sample:

The current study's target population consists of eleventh grade students enrolled in various government higher secondary schools within the district Srinagar. A sample of 476 students was drawn from different higher secondary schools using a simple random sampling technique.

➤ Tools used:

Academic resilience scale developed by Mallick and Kaur (2016) was used as a tool to collect data for measuring the level of Academic Resilience. The scale consists of 52 items divided into 5 areas: Academic confidence, Sense of wellbeing, Motivation and Ability to get goals, Relation with peers & adults, Emotional regulation and physical health. As per norms of the Academic Resilience scale constructed by Mallick and Kaur (2016), the adolescents who obtained score of ‘>=+2.01’ are considered having extremely high level of Academic Resilience. The adolescents who obtained scores of ‘-0.50 to +0.50’ & ‘<-2.01’ are considered having average/moderate and extremely low level of academic Resilience respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The primary objective of the study was “to study the Academic Resilience of Adolescent Students”. To achieve this objective and to decide Academic Resilience of students, the scores were calculated. The details in **Table 1** display the frequency and percentage of Academic Resilience among Adolescent students. On scrutinising Table 1 it was found that out of total 476 students, 210 (44.11%) students fall under the extremely high level of Academic Resilience. There are 257 (53.99%) students which fall under average/moderate level of Academic Resilience and 09(1.89%) students fall under extremely low level of Academic Resilience. Academic Resilience enables a child to live a more confident life. This will teach the child to cooperate, communicate, instil moral values, behave appropriately for the circumstance, learn to be calm, learn from experience and so on. All of these abilities will aid the child's development and help him in his professional and personal life. Academic Resilience is a tool that will assist the child in overcoming failures. It is a beneficial trait for all adolescents and will aid in their career development. Parents, teachers, society, and the community all play important roles in the development of Academic Resilience. Academic Resilience is critical for student's academic success as well as their future. It teaches students

how to deal with challenges and help them learn how to tackle a scenario. The observed results are consistent with the findings of Waxman , Gray and Padron 2003 who concluded that Adolescents with high intellectual Academic Resilience can succeed in school even in the face of adversity. Deb and Arora 2012 revealed that individuals who reported high Resilience performed better academically than who reported poor resilience.

Table 2 displays the level of Academic resilience among the male and female adolescent students of district Srinagar. The details in the said table show that out of 476 students, there are 186 male and 290 female students. On scrutinising the table it was found that, out of 186 male students 64 (34.4%) fall under extremely high level of Academic Resilience. There are 115 (1.82%) male students which fall under the average/moderate level of Academic

Resilience and 07(3.76%) male students fall under extremely low level of Academic Resilience. Likewise, out of 290 female students 146 (50.34%) fall under extremely high level of Academic Resilience. There are 142(48.96%) female students which fall under average/ moderate level of Academic Resilience. 02(0.685) female student falls under extremely low level of Academic Resilience. The results also reveal that female students were having highest percentage of extremely high Academic Resilience than the male students. The results are in line with the findings of Morales (2008) who concluded that females outperformed males in showing academic Resilience. Ranjan et al. (2017) revealed that females are higher in Academic Resilience as compared to males. Cecilia & Antony (2017) revealed that girls were found to be more Academically Resilient compared to the boys.

Table 1: Reflecting the frequency and percentage of Adolescent students with different levels of Academic Resilience

Districts	N	Extremely High	Average/Moderate	Extremely Low
Srinagar	476	210 (44.11%)	257 (53.99%)	09 (1.89%)

Fig. 1: Bar graph showing the prevalence of Academic resilience among adolescent students.

Table 2: Reflecting the frequency and percentage of male and female adolescent students with different levels of Academic Resilience.

District	N	Gender	Extremely High	Average/Moderate	Extremely Low
Srinagar	476	Male 186	64 (34.4%)	115 (61.82%)	07 (3.76%)
		Female 290	146 (50.34%)	142 (48.96%)	02 (0.68%)

Fig. 2: Bar graph showing the prevalence of Academic resilience of male and female adolescent students.

IV. CONCLUSION

The outcomes of this study show that Academic Resilience is frequent among a considerable proportion of higher secondary school students. Academic Resilience will undoubtedly assist the child in leading a more confident life. With this, the child will learn to cooperate, communicate, instil moral values, behave appropriately for the circumstances, be calm, learn from experiences and so on and all of these abilities will aid the child's development and help him in his professional and personal life. Academic Resilience is a skill that will assist the child in overcoming his or her worries and disappointments and obtaining a life challenging experience.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Akbari, A., Khormaiee, F., Keshtkar, A., Mehboodi, K., & Amrai, M. (2014). The prediction of test anxiety based on family communication pattern dimensions: The mediating role of academic resilience among first year high school students. *International Journal of School Health*, 1(2), 1-5.
- [2]. Belay, T., & Missaye, M. (2014). Risks, protection factors and resilience among orphan and vulnerable children (OVC) in Ethiopia: Implications for intervention. *International Journal of Psychology and Counselling*, 6(3), 27-31.
- [3]. Buslig, S. M. C. A. (2019). The academic resilience of college students in Kalinga. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 9(6). doi:10.30845/Ijhss.v9n6p7
- [4]. Cecilia N. Mwangi et al., (2017). Correlates of Academic Resilience among Secondary School Students in Kiambu County, Kenya. *Interdisciplinary Education and Psychology*, 1(1):4.
- [5]. Cecilia, N. M. and Anthony, M. I. (2017). Gender Differences in Academic Resilience and Academic Achievement among Secondary School Students in Kiambu County, Kenya. *Psychology and Behavioral Science International Journal*, 5(5): 555673. doi: 10.19080/PBSIJ.2017.05.555673.
- [6]. Deb, A., & Arora, M. (2012). Resilience and academic achievement among adolescents. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 38(1), 93–101.
- [7]. Gizir, C. A., & Aydin, G. (2009). Protective factors contributing to the academic resilience of students living in poverty in Turkey. *Professional School Counselling*, 13(1), 2156759X0901300103.
- [8]. Ismael-Lennon, A. A. (2010). An Examination of Academic Resilience Among High-Achieving Hispanic-American Male Inner City Adolescents.
- [9]. JJ, R. R., & Vijayalaxmi, A. H. M. (2017). Influence of intervention program to foster academic resilience among adolescents. *Age*, 13(14), 24.
- [10]. Jowkar, B., Kohoulat, N., & Zakeri, H. (2011): "Family communication patterns and academic resilience. *Procedia- Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 29, 87-90. Doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.11.210"
- [11]. Jowkar, B., Kojuri, J., Kohoulat, N., & Hayat, A. A. (2014). Academic resilience in education: the role of achievement goal orientations. *Journal of Advances in Medical Education & Professionalism*, 2(1), 33.
- [12]. Mallick, M. K., & Kaur, S. (2016). Academic resilience among senior secondary school students: Influence of learning environment. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 8(2), 20-27.
- [13]. Mirza, M. S., & Arif, M. I. (2018). Fostering Academic Resilience of Students at Risk of Failure at Secondary School Level. *Journal of Behavioural Sciences*, 28(1).
- [14]. Rajan, S. K., Harifa, P. R., & Pienyu, R. (2017). Academic resilience, locus of control, academic engagement and self-efficacy among the school children. *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology*, 8(4), 507-511.
- [15]. Rao, P.S., & Krishnamurthy, A. (2018). Impact of academic resilience on the scholastic performance of high school students. *Indian Journal of Mental Health*, 5(4), 453-462.
- [16]. Saverimuthu, D. C. (2015). Resilience Factors in School Youth: Looking through Gender and Cultural Lenses.

- [17]. Morales, E. E. (2008). Exceptional female students of color: Academic resilience and gender in higher education. *Innovative Higher Education*, 33(3), 197-213.
- [18]. Morales, E. E. (2010). Linking strengths: Identifying and exploring protective factor clusters in academically resilient low-socioeconomic urban students of color. *Romper Review*, 32(3), 164-175.
- [19]. Mokoena, E. M. (2010). An investigation into the relationship between gender, socioeconomic status, exposure to violence and resilience in a sample of students at the University of the Western Cape (Doctoral dissertation, University of the Western Cape).
- [20]. Monika, D., & Shikha, A.R. (2020). A Study of Academic Resilience among Students of Secondary and Higher Secondary Schools *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 9(5), 1539-1542. DOI: 10.21275/SR20526175818
- [21]. Wang, M., & Gordon, H. R. (1994). A simple, moderately accurate, atmospheric correction algorithm for SeaWiFS. *Remote sensing of environment*, 50(3), 231-239.
- [22]. Waxman, H. C., Gray, J. P., & Padron, Y. N. (2003). Review of research on educational resilience. Centre for research on education, diversity & excellence, university of Houston.